

BROCARD'S PROBLEM PROOF AND SOLUTION OF RAMANUJAN'S EQUATION

Abstract. In this paper we give a conclusive proof to BROCARD'S stuck history problem until this moment. The idea of our proof be clear when we found a simular formula to the BROCARD'S equation (pythagorean equation) that led us to geometry domain which was the hidden piece that revealed the mystery from the problem by using absurdity proof. After that we generalized this method to study the Ramanujan Diophantine equation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Henri Brocard [2,3] , a French mathematician, between 1876 and 1885 posed an article talk about issue [1] , and then rediscovered by Srinivasa Ramanujan, [4] Indian mathematician in 1913. This problem is stated in a more formal way.

Problem 1.1. For what positive integers n is the equation

$$n! + 1 = m^2 \tag{1}$$

satisfied for some positive integer m ?

There are only three known solutions. Ordered paires (n, m) that satisfy the equation are known as Brown Numbers. The only three known paires of Brown Numbers are $(4, 5)$, $(5, 11)$, $(7, 71)$. More formally, Brocard's Problem asks this question : Does n and m exist such that (1) other than for $n \in \{4, 5, 7\}$? In other words, Do more paires of Brown Numbers exist other than $(4, 5)$, $(5, 11)$, $(7, 71)$?

In this paper we transforme the Brocard's algebra problem to geometrie equivalent problem for more clairity and more details and finally make this issue simple and manageable.

Problem progressing 1.2. Starting from (1) wich is equivalent to this equation

$$\sqrt{n!}^2 + 1^2 = m^2 \quad (\text{Pythagorean formal of Brocard's Problem}) \tag{2}$$

In Geometrie, the pervious equations means that we have a right angled triangles all of them have a same side (with lenght of 1) and other side (with lenght of $\sqrt{n!}$) and hypotenuse (with lenght of m). Brown Numbers : $(4, 5)$, $(5, 11)$, $(7, 71)$ in using equation (2) means the existing of three right angled triangles as shown :

$(4, 5)$

$(5, 11)$

$(7, 71)$

Notation 1.1. The three previous hight angled triangles i named them with the Brown tringles

Problem reformulation 1.3. Now we can change Brocard's questions which is : Do more pairs of Brown Numbers exist other than (4 , 5) , (5 , 11) , (7 , 71) ? to this equivalent question : are there other high angles such that (2) is check ?.

To prove that there is just the three Brown numbers is equivalent to prove that there is just the Brown triangles, but before that we are going to do some analyses, for exemple :

β_1 and γ_1 are two angles such us : $\beta_1 + \gamma_1 = 90^\circ$, $\begin{cases} \cos(\beta_1) = \frac{\sqrt{4!}}{5} \\ \sin(\beta_1) = \frac{1}{5} \end{cases}$, $\sqrt{4!}^2 + 1^2 = 5^2$

$\begin{cases} \cos(\gamma_1) = \frac{1}{5} \\ \sin(\gamma_1) = \frac{\sqrt{4!}}{5} \end{cases}$,

$$s = \int_0^{\sqrt{4!}} \tan(\beta_1) x dx = \int_0^{\sqrt{4!}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{4!}} x dx = \left[\frac{x^2}{2\sqrt{4!}} \right]_0^{\sqrt{4!}} = \frac{\sqrt{4!}}{2}$$

we find : $\beta_1 \approx 11,5369590328^\circ$ and $\gamma_1 \approx 78,4630409672^\circ$ so we can say that :
binary solutions (4 , 5) are related with binary angles (β_1 , γ_1)" it means the existing of (4 , 5) means the existing of (β_1 , γ_1) and the oposit is true "

By similar steps we find : (5 , 11) \leftrightarrow (β_1 , γ_1) and (7 , 71) \leftrightarrow (β_2 , γ_2) such us :

$$\beta_2 \approx 5,2159085699^\circ \text{ and } \gamma_2 \approx 84,7840914301^\circ$$

$$\beta_3 \approx 0,8070094906^\circ \text{ and } \gamma_3 \approx 89,1929905094^\circ$$

Remark 1.1. $4 < 5 \leftrightarrow \beta_1 < \gamma_1$ and $5 < 11 \leftrightarrow \beta_2 < \gamma_2$ and $7 < 71 \leftrightarrow \beta_3 < \gamma_3$
 this means when 4 is less than 5 in the first binary solution the angle β_1 is also less than γ_1 in the first Brown triangles and so on.

Remark 1.2. We can note that when n and m increase the angles β_i decrease and angles γ_i increase $\forall i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$

The idea of proof is that we are going to consider that it exist at least one other high angled triangle fulfills all the previous conditions and such for some contradictions, So by using the reasoning by absurd we discover that there is no other Brown Triangles which means that there is no other Brown Numbers.

$$\beta + \gamma = 90^\circ, \quad \begin{cases} \cos(\beta) = \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} \\ \sin(\beta) = \frac{1}{m} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \cos(\gamma) = \frac{1}{m} \\ \sin(\gamma) = \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} \end{cases}, \quad \sqrt{n!}^2 + 1^2 = m^2, \quad n! \in \mathbb{N}^*, m \in \mathbb{N}^*$$

$$\sqrt{n!} \in \mathbb{R}_+^*, n! = m^2 \cos(\beta)^2, 1 = m^2 \sin(\beta)^2, n \in \mathbb{N}^*$$

$$n! + 1 = m^2 \cos(\beta)^2 + m^2 \sin(\beta)^2 \quad (\text{trigonometric equation})$$

$$s = \int_0^{\sqrt{n!}} \tan(\beta) x \, dx = \int_0^{\sqrt{n!}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n!}} x \, dx = \left[\frac{x^2}{2\sqrt{n!}} \right]_0^{\sqrt{n!}} = \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{2} \Rightarrow \sqrt{n!} = 2s$$

$$\Rightarrow n! = 4s^2$$

Notation 1.3.1. this equation : $n! + 1 = m^2$ is equivalent to : $4s^2 + 1 = m^2$ i named it area equation.

Proof 2.1. Resonating by absurd we suppose that at least we have one high angled triangle and let us discuss all possible situations :

1st situation : $0^\circ < \beta < \beta_3$ (or $\gamma_3 < \gamma < 90^\circ$)

$$\cos(\beta_3) < \cos(\beta) < \cos(0^\circ)$$

$$\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{71}\right)^2} < \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} < 1$$

Notation 2.1. we suppose : $\alpha = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{71}\right)^2}$

$$\alpha m < \sqrt{n!} < m \quad (\text{note that : } 0^\circ < \beta < \beta_3 \Rightarrow \sin(0^\circ) < \sin(\beta) < \sin(\beta_3))$$

$$\Rightarrow 0 < \frac{1}{m} < \frac{1}{71}$$

$$\Rightarrow m > 71 \Rightarrow \boxed{m \in \{72, 73, \dots\}}$$

$$\alpha^2 m^2 < n! < m^2 \Leftrightarrow \alpha^2 m^2 < \sqrt{n!}^2 < m^2 \Rightarrow \alpha^2 m^2 + 1 < \sqrt{n!}^2 + 1 < m^2 + 1$$

Because that we have : $\sqrt{n!}^2 + 1 = m^2$ so we get :

$$\alpha^2 m^2 + 1 < m^2 < m^2 + 1 \Leftrightarrow \left[1 - \left(\frac{1}{71}\right)^2\right] m^2 + 1 < m^2 < m^2 + 1$$

$$\Leftrightarrow m^2 - \frac{m^2}{5041} + 1 < m^2 < m^2 + 1 \Rightarrow 1 - \frac{m^2}{5041} < 0 < 1 \Rightarrow 1 < \frac{m^2}{5041} < 1$$

$\Rightarrow 5041 < m^2 < 5041 \Rightarrow m < 71$ so this is contradiction ($m > 71$) which means that there is no right angled triangle in this situation.

2nd situation : $\beta_3 < \beta < \beta_2$ (or $\gamma_2 < \gamma < \gamma_3$)

$$\cos(\beta_2) < \cos(\beta) < \cos(\beta_3)$$

$$\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{11}\right)^2} < \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} < \alpha$$

Notation 2.2. we suppose : $\delta = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{11}\right)^2}$

$$\delta m < \sqrt{n!} < \alpha m \text{ (note that : } \beta_3 < \beta < \beta_2 \Rightarrow \sin(\beta_3) < \sin(\beta) < \sin(\beta_2)$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{71} < \frac{1}{m} < \frac{1}{11} \Rightarrow 11 < m < 71 \Rightarrow m \in \{12, 13, 14, \dots, 69, 70\}$$

$$\delta^2 m^2 < n! < \alpha^2 m^2 \Rightarrow \text{if } m = 12 : \delta^2 12^2 < n! < \alpha^2 12^2 \Rightarrow n! = 143$$

$\Rightarrow n! + 1 = m^2 \Leftrightarrow 143 + 1 = 144 = 12^2$ although the pythagorean equation checked but we have a contradiction which is $n! = 143 \Rightarrow n \in \mathbb{N}^*$ which is impossible to find n such that $n! = 143$.

We will get a similar contradictions after we extract all $n!$ Rest values, which means that there is no right angled triangle in this situation.

3rd situation : $\beta_2 < \beta < \beta_1$ (or $\gamma_1 < \gamma < \gamma_2$)

$$\cos(\beta_1) < \cos(\beta) < \cos(\beta_2)$$

$$\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^2} < \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} < \delta$$

Notation 2.3. we suppose : $\varphi = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^2}$

$\varphi m < \sqrt{n!} < \delta m$ (note that : $\beta_2 < \beta < \beta_1 \Rightarrow \sin(\beta_2) < \sin(\beta) < \sin(\beta_1)$)

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{11} < \frac{1}{m} < \frac{1}{5} \Rightarrow 5 < m < 11 \Rightarrow \boxed{m \in \{6, 7, \dots, 9, 10\}}$$

$\varphi^2 m^2 < n! < \delta^2 m^2 \Rightarrow$ if $m = 6$: $\varphi^2 6^2 < n! < \delta^2 6^2 \Rightarrow n! = 35$

$\Rightarrow n! + 1 = m^2 \Leftrightarrow 35 + 1 = 36 = 6^2$ although the pythagorean equation cheked but we have a contradiction wich is $n! = 35 \Rightarrow n \in \mathbb{N}^*$ which is impossible to find n such that $n! = 35$.

We will get a similar contradictions after we extract all $n!$ Rest values, which means that there is no hight angled triangle in this situation.

4th situation : $\beta_1 < \beta < 90^\circ$ (or $0 < \gamma < \gamma_1$)

$\cos(90^\circ) < \cos(\beta) < \cos(\beta_1)$

$$0 < \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} < \varphi$$

$0 < \sqrt{n!} < \varphi m$ (note that : $\beta_1 < \beta < 90^\circ \Rightarrow \sin(\beta_1) < \sin(\beta) < \sin(90^\circ)$)

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{5} < \frac{1}{m} < 1 \Rightarrow 1 < m < 5 \Rightarrow \boxed{m \in \{2, 3, 4\}}$$

$0 < n! < \varphi^2 m^2 \Rightarrow$ if $m = 2$: $0 < n! < \varphi^2 2^2 \Rightarrow n! = 1$ or $n! = 2$ or $n! = 3$

when $n! = 1$: $n! + 1 = m^2 \Leftrightarrow 1 + 1 = 2 = \sqrt{2}^2 \Rightarrow m = \sqrt{2} \in \mathbb{N}^*$ which is a contradiction.

when $n! = 2$: $n! + 1 = m^2 \Leftrightarrow 2 + 1 = 3 = \sqrt{3}^2 \Rightarrow m = \sqrt{3} \in \mathbb{N}^*$ which is a contradiction.(also we can say : is impossible to find n such that $n! = 3$.)

when $n! = 3$ we also find a contradiction. wich means that there is no hight angled triangle in this situation.

After descussion all the possible situations and finding in each one a contradiction, we can conclude (by absurd) that there is no other hight angled triangle satisfies the previous conditions with other words there is no other solutions for the equation (1). So Brocard's Problem solved.

Remark 1.2. We can also find other contradictions in the previous situations.

Remark 1.3. We can use the area equation : $4s^2 + 1 = m^2$ which is equivalent to $s = \frac{\sqrt{m^2-1}}{2}$ to find an other way of proof.

Generalisation 3. (Brocard's - Ramanujan problem)

Problem reformulation 3.1.

If we considered the equation $n! + k = m^2$ such that $(n, m, k) \in \mathbb{N}^* \times \mathbb{N}^* \times \mathbb{N}^*$ we can rewrite it like this : $\sqrt{n!}^2 + \sqrt{k}^2 = m^2$ (Pythagorean formal)

$$\beta + \gamma = 90^\circ, \quad \begin{cases} \cos(\beta) = \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} \\ \sin(\beta) = \frac{\sqrt{k}}{m} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \cos(\gamma) = \frac{\sqrt{k}}{m} \\ \sin(\gamma) = \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} \end{cases}$$

$$\sqrt{n!}^2 + \sqrt{k}^2 = m^2, n! \in \mathbb{N}^*, m \in \mathbb{N}^*, k \in \mathbb{N}^*, \begin{cases} n! + k = m^2 \cos(\beta)^2 + m^2 \sin(\beta)^2 \\ n! + k = m^2 \cos(\gamma)^2 + m^2 \sin(\gamma)^2 \end{cases}$$

$$n \in \mathbb{N}^*, s = \int_0^{\sqrt{n!}} \text{tang}(\beta)x \, dx = \int_0^{\sqrt{n!}} \frac{\sqrt{k}}{\sqrt{n!}}x \, dx = \left[\frac{\sqrt{k}x^2}{2\sqrt{n!}} \right]_0^{\sqrt{n!}} = \frac{\sqrt{k}\sqrt{n!}}{2}$$

$$\Rightarrow \sqrt{n!} = \frac{2s}{\sqrt{k}} \Rightarrow n! = \frac{4s^2}{k}$$

Notation 3.1. this equation : $n! + k = m^2$ is equivalent to : $\frac{4s^2}{k} + k = m^2$ i named it area equation.

Problem solving 3.2.

Obviously, there are only three possible situations for the angles β and γ which are : $\beta = \gamma$ or $\beta < \gamma$ or $\beta > \gamma$

1st situation : $\beta = \gamma$ there is just one angle satisfies this situation which is $\frac{\pi}{4}$ (45°) because we have a hight angled triangle.

$$\begin{cases} \cos(\beta) = \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} \\ \sin(\beta) = \frac{\sqrt{k}}{m} \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) = \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} \\ \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) = \frac{\sqrt{k}}{m} \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} = \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} \dots\dots (1) \\ \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} = \frac{\sqrt{k}}{m} \dots\dots (2) \end{cases} \Rightarrow \text{from (2) we get :}$$

$$m = \frac{2\sqrt{k}}{\sqrt{2}} \Rightarrow \text{substituting in (1) we get : } \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} = \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{\frac{2\sqrt{k}}{\sqrt{2}}} \Rightarrow \sqrt{n!} = \sqrt{k} \Rightarrow \boxed{n! = k}$$

When we substitute in equation we find : $n! + k = m^2 \Rightarrow k + k = m^2 \Rightarrow 2k = m^2$
 $\Rightarrow \boxed{m = \sqrt{2}\sqrt{k}}$ because that we have $m \in \mathbb{N}^*$ it is necessary that k is on form
of : $\boxed{k = 2b^2}$ such that $b \in \mathbb{N}^*$. So $n! = 2b^2$, $b \in \mathbb{N}^*$

The solutions are trios : $(n!, k, m) = (2b^2, 2b^2, \sqrt{2}\sqrt{2b^2})$ so we need just to find
 $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$ such that $n! = 2b^2$

Exemples for solutions : if $b = 1$ we get : $k = 2 \Rightarrow m = 2$ and $n! = 2 \Rightarrow n = 2$

So we have $2! + 2 = 2^2$ which is true. $(2, 2, 2)$ is a solution.

if $b = 2$ we get : $k = 8 \Rightarrow m = 4$ and $n! = 8 \Rightarrow$ we can not find n such that $n! = 8$
so there is no solution.

if $b = 14200201778964$ we get : $k = 26! \Rightarrow m = 28400403557929$ and $n! = 26!$
we have $26! + 26! = 28400403557929^2$ wich is true. $(26!, 26!, 28400403557929)$ is a
solution. So on.

When $\beta = \gamma = \frac{\pi}{4}$ the equation has solutions on form : $(n!, k, m) = (2b^2, 2b^2, \sqrt{2}\sqrt{2b^2})$
and we have hight angled triangles (and isosceles) like this one :

Notation 3.2.1. these isosceles hight angled triangled i named them feroukhi triangles.

Remark 3.1. in 2nd and 3rd situation we are going to suppose that we have at least one hight
angled triangle fulfills all the previous conditions and find at least one contradiction then by
absurd we can say that there is no hight angled trinagled.

2nd situation : $\beta < \gamma$ which means certainly $0 < \beta < \frac{\pi}{4}$ and $\frac{\pi}{4} < \gamma < \frac{\pi}{2}$

$$\sin(\beta) = \frac{\sqrt{k}}{m} \Rightarrow m = \frac{\sqrt{k}}{\sin(\beta)} \Rightarrow \cos(\beta) = \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{\sqrt{k}} \Rightarrow \sqrt{n!} = \frac{\cos(\beta)\sqrt{k}}{\sin(\beta)}$$

$$\Rightarrow n! = \frac{\cos(\beta)^2 k}{\sin(\beta)^2} = \frac{k}{\tan(\beta)^2}$$

$$\Rightarrow \sin(0) < \sin(\beta) < \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \Rightarrow 0 < \frac{\sqrt{k}}{m} < \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \Rightarrow m > \frac{2\sqrt{k}}{\sqrt{2}} \Rightarrow m > \sqrt{2}\sqrt{k} \dots \dots (1)$$

$$\Rightarrow 0 < \sin(\beta)^2 < \frac{1}{2}$$

$$0 < \beta < \frac{\pi}{4} \Rightarrow \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) < \cos(\beta) < \cos(0) \Rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} < \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} < 1 \Rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{2}m}{2} < \sqrt{n!} < m \dots \dots (2)$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{2} < \cos(\beta)^2 < 1 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{k} < n!$$

Remark 3.2. (2) $\Rightarrow \frac{m^2}{2} < n! < m^2 \Rightarrow \frac{m^2}{2} + k < n! + k < m^2 + k$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{m^2}{2} + k < m^2 < m^2 + k \Rightarrow \frac{m^2}{2} + k - m^2 < 0 < k \Rightarrow \frac{2k - m^2}{2} < 0 < k$$

$k < \frac{m^2}{2} < k \Rightarrow 2k < m^2 < 2k \Rightarrow m < \sqrt{2}\sqrt{k}$ which is a contradiction with (1) so there is no right angled triangle.

3rd situation : $\beta > \gamma$ which means certainly $\frac{\pi}{4} < \beta < \frac{\pi}{2}$ and $0 < \gamma < \frac{\pi}{4}$

$$\Rightarrow \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) < \sin(\beta) < \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \Rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} < \frac{\sqrt{k}}{m} < 1 \Rightarrow m > \frac{2\sqrt{k}}{\sqrt{2}} \Rightarrow m > \sqrt{2}\sqrt{k} \dots \dots (1)$$

$$\Rightarrow 0 < \sin(\beta)^2 < \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\frac{\pi}{4} < \beta < \frac{\pi}{2} \Rightarrow \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) < \cos(\beta) < \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) \Rightarrow 0 < \frac{\sqrt{n!}}{m} < \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \Rightarrow 0 < \sqrt{n!} < \frac{\sqrt{2}m}{2} \dots \dots (2)$$

Remark 3.3. (2) $\Rightarrow 0 < n! < \frac{m^2}{2} \Rightarrow k < n! + k < \frac{m^2}{2} + k$

Because that we have : $n! + k = m^2$ so we get :

$$\Rightarrow k < m^2 < \frac{m^2}{2} + k \Rightarrow k - m^2 < 0 < \frac{m^2}{2} - m^2 + k \Rightarrow k - m^2 < 0 < \frac{2k - m^2}{2} \dots \dots (*)$$

Because that we have $m^2 > 2k > k \Rightarrow k - m^2 < 0$ and we have $2k - m^2 < 0$ so (*) means that 0 is between two negative numbers which is a contradiction. So we don't have any right angled triangle.

Remark 3.4. we can use the area equation : $\frac{4s^2}{k} + k = m^2$ which is equivalent to $s = \frac{\sqrt{km^2 - k^2}}{2}$ to find another way of proof.

Conclusion 3. When $\alpha = \beta = \frac{\pi}{4}$ we found solutions (many isosceles right angled triangles) which are $(n!, k, m) = (2b^2, 2b^2, \sqrt{2}\sqrt{2b^2})$.

When $\beta > \gamma$ which means $\beta \in \left] \frac{\pi}{4}, \frac{\pi}{2} \right[$ and $\gamma \in \left] 0, \frac{\pi}{4} \right[$

there are no solutions (after using absurdity reasoning).

When $\beta < \gamma$ which means $\beta \in \left] 0, \frac{\pi}{4} \right[$ and $\gamma \in \left] \frac{\pi}{4}, \frac{\pi}{2} \right[$ there are solutions

With the previous method we can also discuss this equation : $n! = m^2$ (feroukhi equation)

I will publish about it in my next paper.

References

- [1] R.K. Guy, Unsolved Problems in Number Theory, third ed. Problem Books in Math, Springer-Verlag, New York, 2004.
- [2] H. Brocard, Question 166, Nouv. Corresp. Math. 2 (1876) 287.
- [3] H. Brocard, Question 1532, Nouv. Ann. Math. 4 (1885) 291.
- [4] S. Ramanujan, Question 469, J. Indian Math. Soc, 5 (1913) 59.